

The Effect Of Climate Change On Human Comfort In Nineveh And Basra Governorates Using The Heat Discomfort And Discomfort Index (DI)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 16, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Climate Change, Human Comfort, Nineveh And Basra Climate</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5027433</p>	<p><i>The study aims to reveal the impact of climatic changes on human comfort in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra; this is due to its direct and indirect importance to human comfort, activity and health. The study relies on knowing the relationship between the effect of climate change and human comfort on the thermal disturbance index (DI), and the data required for all climatic elements of the two weather monitoring stations (Mosul, Basra), for a period of time It reached (69) years, and it fell between the years (2018-1950), and the study found that there are differences in the bioclimatic categories during the months of the year between the governorates of Nineveh and Basra in (April, May, June, July, September, October), and changes in In the line of general trends of values and the frequencies of their types during the study period with (increasing and decreasing), Nineveh Governorate recorded an increase in the general trend line of (DI) values, and a positive annual change during the study period in all months of the year, as well as the linear trends of the frequencies of C, the two classes decreased. MD), and increased in (ED, SD, RHS), and Basra governorate recorded a decrease and negative change in the months (January, February, March, November, December), and the general trend line increased in the two categories (C, RHS) and decreased in (MD, SD, ED) and the biological varieties varied in their total frequencies and percentages, so the class (C) appeared in the first place, and the last place was the class (ED).</i></p>

Introduction

The issue of climate change is clear and unambiguous, and many of the changes that have been observed since the fifties of the twentieth century are unprecedented over decades to thousands of years, and these changes have affected natural and human systems on all continents of the world. (Climate change, 2014, p. 6, 2). The problem of climate change is one of the problems facing all countries of the world, and the issue of climate change is of great importance in climate studies. As human activity and comfort are affected by the problems caused by climatic changes, such as the problem of imbalance in the gases that make up the atmosphere due to the accumulation of barrier and greenhouse gases, and for the purpose of reaching physiological comfort, bioclimatic studies have appeared on the basis of the relationship between humans and climate, among which are classifications and criteria. In its relations to a number of climatic elements (solar radiation, temperature, humidity, and wind) that affect a person's sense of weather and his feeling of comfort and discomfort; As the state of adaptation varies according to the age group, gender, age, health status, mood, type of clothing, the nature of the person's activity and the environment in which he lives. Because it represents the balance between heat lost and heat gained in the body.

The spatial boundaries of the study

The study area in Iraq is the governorates of Nineveh and Basra; Nineveh Governorate is located between latitudes (55-34-03-37) in the north, and between longitudes (25-41° - 25-44) in the east. Dohuk, to the east by the governorates of Erbil and Tamim, to the south by the governorates of Salah al-Din and Anbar, and to the west by the Syrian Arab Republic. Basra Governorate is located in the far southern part of Iraq, and extends between latitudes (05-29-20-30) in the north, and longitudes (40-46-30-48) in the east, and it is bordered by the governorates of Maysan and DhiQar from the north, and the Iraqi borders Iran in the east, the Iraqi and Kuwaiti borders and the Arabian Gulf in the south, and Al-Muthanna Governorate in the west. See map (1).

Map (1) the study area and the stations included in the two governorates

The Thom Discomfort DI

This guide or indicator was proposed and applied by (Thom and Bosen) in 1959 and is regarded as one of the best and most representative criteria for evaluating influence temperature; Because it expresses the values of The Thom Discomfort and the combined effect of temperature, relative humidity and aerodynamics on the sensation of heat felt by the human body, and this evidence is applicable in a wide range of climates where temperatures reach (47) (°C. Mihăilă, D., et al. 2016, p.6)) was used by (Thom) to express the feeling of discomfort of office workers due to climatic conditions in the United States, and this evidence is appropriate for hot weather; It shows the effect of heat and humidity on the human body, not cold. It is also considered one of the most widely used criteria for its ease of application, and because human bioclimatic comfort is highly correlated with temperature and humidity in the air. The human body, and then the body's ability to carry out the process of self-cooling was weakened; Because the evaporation process helps the body get rid of excess heat, especially in summer. (Abu Rahil, 2019, p. 141).

(Thom) found a series of boundary values for the (DI) index that indicate the degrees of discomfort, for example, when the value is less than (21) degrees Celsius, people did not feel any discomfort, but when the value reaches (24) degrees Celsius, they feel more than (50%) of the people tested for thermal discomfort, and with the increase in the values, the level of thermal discomfort increases. Annoyance index values greater than (30) indicate the feeling of (100%) of the population in discomfort, and the level of medical emergency was determined when the value exceeds (32) (Stathopoulou, MI, et al. 2005, p.5). The effect of climatic disturbance and discomfort occurs as a result of high temperatures, and this equation has never been applied at the local level in Iraq; It has been applied in several countries, including Greece, Indonesia, Malaysia and Moldova, and depends on the elements (temperature - relative humidity) in its applied formula to extract the results of values and their types. Table (1) shows the relationship between DI Thom values and the vital climatic conditions and thermal interactions of the human body.

The thermal nuisance and discomfort index (DI) is used when applying the following empirical formula:

$$\text{DI Thom (C)} = (0.8 * T_{usc}) + [0.08 * (U_r - 3.2)]$$

Thermal Disturbance Proof = DI Thom (C)

Average monthly temperature = T_{usc}

Monthly Relative Humidity = U_r

Equation constants = (0.8, 0.08, 2.3)

Table (1) Limits of values, their vital classes and their abbreviations according to the Thom DI

No	bioclimatic classes	abbreviation	Biological class values limits	Vital species
1	Comfort	C	DI > 21	(Comfortable) without heat

				disturbance
2	Slight discomfort	SD	21 < DI > 24	The slight thermal disturbance
3	Moderate discomfort	MD	24 < DI > 27	The inconvenience heat of the m mediate
4	Enhanced discomfort	ED	27 < DI > 29	Increased thermal disturbance
5	Risk of heat shock	R H S	DI < 29	Risk exposure Z to shock the thermal

The general trend of thermal nuisance index (DI) values in Nineveh and Basra governorates. The change in the general trend of the thermal disturbance index (DI) values for each month during the study period will be analyzed to find out the comfortable and uncomfortable months, and for the purpose of revealing the increase, decreasing, annual change and the change occurring during the study period according to this relative evidence), and their impact on the comfort of the population in the provinces of Nineveh and Basra , as follows:

January

January is characterized by being the coldest cold month in winter in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra; The average temperature during the study period in Mosul station reached (7.0), and in Basra station (12.5), Nineveh governorate is located within the limits of category C) according to the (DI) index, where the general average of values was (11.7 C) in The Mosul station, as for Basra governorate, was also represented by category (C), so the general average of values in the Basra station reached (15.5 C, see Table (2). This month witnesses a noticeable change and variation in the linear trends of (DI) values between the two governorates, indicating about The increase in Nineveh Governorate, which means more disturbing for the population, is evident from Figure (1), as it is evident from the registration of the Mosul station that an annual positive rate of change amounted to (0.051%) and during the study period (3.519%), see Table (3), as for Basra Governorate. The general trend line of values indicates decreasing, as shown by the trend line in Figure (2), meaning that it tends to be more comfortable, as the Basra station recorded a negative annual rate of change of (-0.089%) and during the study period (-6.141%). Table (3), and notes the variation and difference in the general trend line of values and the annual rate of change and the change during the study period between the two provinces.

Table (2) monthly averages of DI values and their biological classes in Nineveh and Basra governorates for the period (1950-2018)

Nov	Dec	Oct	Sep	Aug	Jul	Jun	Ma y	Apr	Mar	Feb	Jan	)DI(	statio n
12.8	15.9	20.6	25.2	28.8	29.3	26.9	23.0	19.2	15.6	12.9	11.7	the average	Mosul
C	C	C	MD	ED	RHS	MD	SD	C	C	C	C	item	
16.4	20.1	25.2	29.1	31.3	31.5	30.3	28.0	23.8	19.7	16.8	15.5	the average	Basra
C	C	MD	RHS	RHS	RHS	RH S	ED	SD	C	C	C	item	

Source: The researcher based on the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority, Iraq, Baghdad.

Figure (1) the general trend of (DI) values at the Mosul station as Jan

Figure (2) The general trend of (DI) values in Basra station for the month of Jan

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (3) the linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of January in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
3.519	0.051	0.006	-0.2062	69	11.7	Mosul
-6.141	-0.089	-0.0138	42.957	69	15.5	Basra

Source: The researcher based on Table (2), Figures (1, 2), and the annual change equation ($C = bi / y * 100$).

February

February is considered one of the coldest months of the year in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra, as the average temperature reached (9.1) o in the Mosul station and (15.0) in the Basra station during the study period, and it predominates in Nineveh governorate with the (C) category. (DI) During the study period in Mosul station (12.9°C), as for Basra governorate, it was represented by category (C) also, the general average in Basra station reached (16.8°C), see table (2). It is clear this month that the general trend line The values in Nineveh governorate are on the increase to become more disturbing to the population, as shown in Figure (3). It appears that the Mosul station recorded a positive annual change rate (0.077%) that reached (5.313%) during the study period. Table (4) sees, in Basra governorate The general trend of the values differed, it indicates decreasing to be more comfortable, as it appears in Figure (4); Basra station recorded a negative annual rate of change of (-0.041%) whose amount reached (-2.829%) during the study period, see Table (4).

Figure (3) The general trend of (DI) values at the Mosul station

Figure (4) The general trend of (DI) values at the Basra February station

Source: The researcher equation of the Index (DI), Meteorological and Seismic Table (4) the linear in (DI) values for the month governorates of Nineveh (1950-2018)

based on the results of the and the data of the Iraqi Monitoring Authority. relationship of the change of February in the and Basra for the period

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	)C(Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
5.313	0.077	0.01	-7.0593	69	12.9	Mosul
-2.829	-0.041	-0.0069	30.5	69	16.8	Basra

Source: the researcher based on Table (2), Figures (3, 4), and the annual change equation (C).

March

Temperatures begin to rise gradually in this month to be more moderate; The average temperature reached (13.0) ° in the Mosul station and (19.5) ° in the Basra station during the study period, and the category (C) in Nineveh Governorate was represented by a general average of 15.6 degrees Celsius in the Mosul station, while in Basra it reached The overall average of the results of the values (C (19.7)) was represented by the category (C), see table (2). It is clear that the general trends of values are towards increasing in Nineveh Governorate, and this means that they tend to be less comfortable and more disturbing for the population, as can be seen from figure (5); As the Mosul station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.087%) and (6.003%) during the study period, see table (5). As for Basra governorate, the general trend line indicates a decrease so that the values are more comfortable for the population, as shown in the figure (6); As the Basra station recorded a negative annual change rate of (-0.002%) and during the study period (0.138%), see table (5).

Figure (5) the general trend of (DI) values at the Mosul March station

Figure (6) the general trend of (DI) values at Basra Adar Station

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (5) the linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of March in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
6.003	0.087	0.0137	-11,531	69	15.6	Mosul
-0.138	-0.002	-0.0004	20,581	69	19.7	Basra

Source: The researcher based on Table (2), Figures (5, 6), and the annual change equation (C).

April

Temperatures continued to rise gradually in this month, with moderate weather in the two governorates, as the average temperature reached (18.2) o in the Mosul station and (25.4) in the Basra station during the study period, and the (C) category prevails in Nineveh governorate with a general average of (19.2 C) in Mosul station, while in Basra governorate, the (SD) variety was represented, and the general average of values reached (23.8 C), see table (2). It is noted in this month that the linear trends of (DI) values tend to increase in Nineveh Governorate to be less comfortable and disturbing for the population. Figure (7), and the data in Table (6) indicate that the Mosul station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.084%) and during the study

period, it reached (5.796%), as for Basra Governorate, it appears that the line of general trends in values tends to increase in this month to be more disturbing for the residents of the governorate, as shown in Figure (8); The Basra station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.010%), and also positive during the study period, which amounted to (0.690%). See table (6).

Figure (7) The general trend of (DI) values at the Mosul station

Figure (8) The general trend of (DI) values at Basra Nissan Station

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (6) the linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of April in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
5.796	0.084	0.0162	-12.978	69	19.2	Mosul
0.690	0.010	0.0024	19,038	69	23.8	Basra

Source: The researcher based on Table (2), Figures (7, 8), and the annual change equation (C).

May

Temperatures continue to rise this month, as the average temperature reached (24.6) in the Mosul station, while it reached (31.5) in the Basra station during the study period. In the Mosul station, and (22.3 C), but in Basra governorate, the (ED) variety prevails in it with a general average of (28.0 C), see Table (2) and it is noted in this month that the linear trends of the (DI) index values are trending Towards an increase in Nineveh governorate to be more annoying to the residents of the governorate, as shown in Figure (9); As the Mosul station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.050%) and during the study period (3.381%), table (7) is seen. As for Basra governorate, it becomes clear this month that the general trends of values are on the increase, which makes it more disturbing as well. This is seen from the trend line in Figure (10); The annual change rate was positive (0.080%) and also during the study period (5.520%). See table (7).

Figure (9) The general trend of (DI) values at Mosul station in May

Figure (10) The general trend of (DI) values at Basra station in May

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (7) The linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of May in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	)C(Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
3.381	0.050	0.0114	0.3563	69	23.0	Mosul
5.520	0.080	0.0225	-16.595	69	28.0	Basra

Source: The researcher based on Table (2), Figures (9, 10), and the annual change equation (C).

June

It is considered one of the hottest months in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra. The average temperature in the Mosul station was (31.0), and in the Basra station, it reached (34.9) during the study period, and the (MD) type prevails in Nineveh governorate with an overall average of (C26.9) in the Mosul station, while it is represented in the governorate of Nineveh. Basra has the highest cultivar (RHS) with a general average of (C30.3) in Basra station, see Table (2). The linear trends of (DI) values indicate that they tend to increase in Nineveh Governorate to approach the disturbance from the (ED) class, which is the increase in thermal disturbance. Note Figure (11); As it appears in the Mosul station, a positive annual change rate of (0.073%) and reached (5.037%) during the study period, see table (8), but in Basra governorate, the general trend line of the values indicates an increase, which makes it more dangerous for the residents of the governorate as it seems Through Figure (12); If the annual change appeared to be positive, it amounted to (0.093%) and during the study period by (6.417%), see Table (8).

Figure (11) The general trend of (DI) values at Mosul station, June

Figure (12) The general trend of (DI) values in Basra station, June

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (8) The linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of June in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	)C(Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
5.037	0.073	0.0199	-12,514	69	26.9	Mosul
6.417	0.093	0.0284	-26.152	69	30.3	Basra

Source: The researcher based on Table (2), Figures (11, 12), and the annual change equation (C).

July

July is the warmest month in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra. The average temperature in Mosul station was (34.4) and Basra station reached (36.5) during the study period, as the dangerous class (RHS) in Nineveh Governorate, which is considered the highest biological climatic class, Mosul station recorded an average of (C29 year-on-year). .3), As for the province of Basra, the RHS variety is also prevalent in this month, with a general average of (31.5 C), see table (2). It is noted from the linear trends of values according to the (DI) index that they tend to increase during the month of July in Nineveh Governorate, as it appears from Figure (13) to be more dangerous and disturbing to the population; As the Mosul station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.036%) that amounted to (2.484%) during the study period, see table (9). As for Basra governorate, the general trend line for values in this month is also heading towards an increase in values to be more dangerous It is disturbing to the population. It is noted in Figure (14); The Basra station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.113%), with a higher rate between stations during the study period, which amounted to (7.797%), see Table (9).

Figure (13) The general trend of (DI) values at the Mosul station, July

Figure (14) The general trend of (DI) values in Basra station, Tammuz

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (9) is the linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of July in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
2.484	0.036	0.0107	8.1237	69	29.3	Mosul
7.797	0.113	0.0356	-39.069	69	31.5	Basra

Source: The researcher based on Table (2), Figures (13, 14), and the annual change equation (C).

August

The month of August is considered one of the warmest months of the year, as temperatures recorded an average of (33.5) in the Mosul station, and (36.0) in the Basra station during the study period in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra, and the (ED) category prevails in Nineveh governorate and its general average was (28.8) C) in the Mosul station, while in Basra governorate, the risk category (RHS) was represented, and the general

average of values was (31.3 C) at the Basra station, see Table (2). The general linear trends of DI values in August indicate that they have increased in Nineveh Governorate to be the most annoying increase for the population, as shown in Figure (15); As we note that the Mosul station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.049%) that reached during the study period (3.381%), see table (10). As for Basra governorate, we notice that the general trend line of values is increasing to become more dangerous and disturbing to the population, as it appears in Figure (16); As the annual rate of change appeared positive by (0.123%) and also during the study period by (8.487%), see table (10).

Figure (15) The general trend of (DI) values at Mosul Ab station

Figure (16) The general trend of (DI) values at the Basra-Ab station

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (10) the linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of August in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes during counting study period of the (%)	C(Annual rate of change (%))	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
3.381	0.049	0.0143	0.5022	69	28.8	Mosul
8.487	0.123	0.0387	-45.499	69	31.3	Basra

Source: The researcher based on Table (2), Figures (15, 16), and the annual change equation (C).

September

It is one of the transitional months, and its thermal characteristics are close to the summer months, so the average temperature in it during the study period was (28.6) in the Mosul station, while its average in the Basra station was (32.9), and the variety was (MD) in Nineveh Governorate, Its general rate was (25.2 C) in the Mosul station, while the Basra governorate has the dangerous type (RHS) with a general average of (29.1 C), see table (2). It is clear from Figure (17) that the general trend line of values has increased in Nineveh Governorate to have a more severe impact on disturbing the population. As the Mosul station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.061%) that amounted to (4.209%) during the study period. Table (11) is seen. As for Basra governorate, the general trend line for values shows an upward trend in this month, making it more dangerous and disturbing. Figure (18); the annual change rate was positive in Basra station by (0.105%), and (7.25%) during the study period.

Figure (17) The general trend of (DI) values at Mosul Station, September

Figure (18) The general trend of (DI) values at Basra September station

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (11) the linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of September in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
4.209	0.061	0.0155	-5.5714	69	25.2	Mosul
7.245	0.105	0.0306	-31.692	69	29.1	Basra

Source: The researcher based on Table (2), Figures (17, 18), and the annual change equation (C).

October

The month of October is characterized by a gradual decrease in temperatures in the two governorates, as the average temperature in the Mosul station reached (21.5) and in the Basra station reached (27.2) during the study period, and these thermal conditions affected the variation in the values of the index (DI) and its climatic categories. vitality; As the (C) variety appears in Nineveh Governorate, the general average of values reached (20.6 C) in the Mosul station, while in Basra Governorate, the (MD) variety was represented in it with a general average of values of (25.2 C) in the Basra station, see Table (2)). It is noted that the linear trends in this month tend to increase in Nineveh Governorate to be less comfortable and more disturbing for the population, as shown in Figure (19); As the Mosul station recorded a positive annual rate of change of (0.102%) that reached (7.038%) during the study period, see table (12). The trend line in Figure (20); the annual change rate was positive (0.079%) and reached (5.451%) during the study period, table (12).

Figure (19) The general trend of (DI) values at Mosul station Oct

Figure (20) The general trend of (DI) values at Basra station Oct

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (12) is the linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of October in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
7.038	0.102	0.0212	-21.373	69	20.6	Mosul
5.451	0.079	0.0201	-14.672	69	25.2	Basra

Source: the researcher based on Table (2), Figures (19, 20), and the annual change equation (C).

November

It is considered a moderate month in terms of temperatures, with a gradual increase in relative humidity rates, and this is evident by the average temperature, as it reached (13.6) degrees in the Mosul station, and (19.5) degrees in the Basra station during the study period, and Nineveh Governorate is within the boundaries of Category (C), as the general average reached (15.9 C) in the Mosul station, as for Basra Governorate, it was represented by category (C), as its general rate reached (20.1 C), see table (2). The month of November witnesses a noticeable difference in the linear trends of (DI) values between the two governorates. As it becomes clear that Nineveh Governorate is on the increase to be less comfortable for the population, Figure (21), and the Mosul station records a positive annual rate of change of (0.088%) and at a rate of (6.072%) during the study period, see table (13), while Basra Governorate has It differed completely in the general trend line from Nineveh Governorate; As the trend appeared in it towards the decreasing, and this means that the values tend to be comfortable as it appears from the trend line in Figure (22), and the registration of the Basra station shows a negative annual rate of change of (-0.051%) and also negative during the study period at a rate of (-3.519%). See table (13).

Figure (21) The general trend of (DI) values at Mosul station Nov

Figure (22) The general trend of (DI) values at Basra Nov

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (13) The linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of November in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
6.072	0.088	0.014	-11.851	69	15.9	Mosul
-3.519	-0.051	-0.0104	40.813	69	20.1	Basra

Source: the researcher based on Table (2), Figures (21, 22), and the annual change equation (C).

December

It is characterized by being one of the cold months in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra; The general average during the study period was (8.5) in the Mosul station, and (13.8) in the Basra station, and the category (C) appears in the Nineveh governorate with an overall average of (12.8 C) in the Mosul station, while in the Basra governorate it was It was also represented by the category (C), so the general average of values reached (16.4 °C) at the Basra station, see Table (2). This month is witnessing a clear change in the line of general trends between the two governorates. It tends to increase in Nineveh Governorate, which makes it less comfortable for the population, as can be seen from the trend in Figure (23). In the Mosul station, an annual change rate of (0.083%) was shown, which amounted to (5.727%) during the study period. Table (14) is seen in the table. As for Basra governorate, the general trend of values differs from that of Nineveh governorate in this month. It is decreasing, and therefore the values tend to be comfortable for the residents of the governorate, as it appears from the trend line in Figure (24). The Basra station recorded a negative annual rate of change of (-0.044%), and during the study period (-3.036%), the table (14).

Figure (23) the general trend of (DI) values at Mosul station as Dec

Figure (24) the general trend of (DI) values at Basra station as Dec

Source: The researcher based on the results of the equation of the Index (DI), and the data of the Iraqi Meteorological and Seismic Monitoring Authority.

Table (14) the linear relationship of the change in (DI) values for the month of December in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra for the period (1950-2018)

for changes t during counting studyperiod of the (%)	)C(Annual rate ofchange (%)	factor direction	fixed limit	The number of years	for the year Pain count(DI)	station
5.727	0.083	0.0107	-8.354	69	12.8	Mosul
-3.036	-0.044	-0.0073	30.954	69	16.4	Basra

Source: the researcher based on Table (2), Figures (23, 24), and the annual change equation (C).

The importance of the study lies in the results it reached, and it concluded with a set of results, namely:

1. The study revealed the variation of biological species during the months of the year according to the (DI) index in the governorates of Nineveh and Basra; It varied in the months (April, May, June, July, September and October).

2. Nineveh Governorate recorded an increase in the general trend line of (DI) values, and a positive annual change during the study period in all months of the year, and the linear trends of the frequencies of the two classes (C, MD) decreased, and increased in (ED, SD, RHS). Basra governorate recorded a decrease and negative change in the months (January, February, March, November, December), and the general trend line increased in the two categories (C, RHS) and decreased in (MD, SD, ED). The sum of its frequencies and proportions, so that the category (C) appeared in the first place, and the last rank was the category (ED).

3. It is noted that the most annual change during the study period in the values of the index (DI) appeared in the Basra station; It reached (8.487) in August, while the lowest annual change appears in Basra station, at -6.141 present in January. The most biological variety that changed during the years of the study was the (RHS) variety, with a change rate of (73.968%) in the Mosul station, and the Basra station recorded the lowest annual change of (-82,248) in the (ED) variety.

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